

Technical Report: Efficient Static Vulnerability Analysis for JavaScript with Multiversion Dependency Graphs

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While static analysis tools that rely on Code Property Graphs (CPGs) to detect security vulnerabilities have proven effective, deciding how much information to include in the graphs remains a challenge. Including less information can lead to a more scalable analysis but at the cost of reduced effectiveness in identifying vulnerability patterns, potentially resulting in classification errors. Conversely, more information in the graph allows for a more effective analysis but may affect scalability. For example, scalability issues have been recently highlighted in ODGen, the state-of-the-art CPG-based tool for detecting Node.js vulnerabilities.

This technical report presents the soundness proofs of a novel graph-based data structure named Multiversion Dependency Graphs (MDGs), presented at PLDI 2024. MDGs explore a new point in the design space of CPGs for JavaScript vulnerability detection, by capturing the state evolution of objects and their properties during program execution. Compared to the graphs used by ODGen, MDGs are significantly simpler without losing key information needed for vulnerability detection. In this document, we provide a complete account of the abstract interpretation-based analysis that computes MDGs for a core of JavaScript, including the proof of its soundness.

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A COMPLETE FORMALIZATION

A.1 Syntax

Syntax [Core JavaScript]

$$\begin{aligned}
 e \in \mathcal{Exp} &::= v \in \mathcal{V} \mid x \in \mathcal{X} \\
 s \in \mathcal{Stm} &::= x := e \mid x :=_i e_1 \oplus e_2 \mid x :=_i e.p \mid x :=_i e_1[e_2] \mid e_1.p :=_i e_2 \mid e_1[e_2] :=_i e_3 \mid x := \{ \}^i \\
 &\mid \text{if}(e)\{s_1\} \text{ else } \{s_2\} \mid \text{while}(e)\{s\} \mid s_1; s_2 \mid x := f(e_1, \dots, e_n)
 \end{aligned}$$

A.2 Abstract Graph Construction

Definition A.1 (Abstract Graph Property Lookup). Given an abstract graph \hat{g} , an abstract location \hat{l} , and a property p , the graph lookup operation on \hat{g} and \hat{l} , written $\hat{g}[\hat{l}, p]$, is formally defined as follows:

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \text{DIRECT LOOKUP - KNOWN PROPERTY} \\
 \frac{\hat{g} = - \uplus \{ \hat{l} \mapsto_{p(p)} \hat{l}' \}}{\hat{g}[\hat{l}, p] \rightsquigarrow \hat{l}'} \\
 \\
 \text{DIRECT LOOKUP - UNKNOWN PROPERTY} \\
 \frac{\hat{g} = - \uplus \{ \hat{l} \mapsto_{p(*)} \hat{l}' \}}{\hat{g}[\hat{l}, p] \rightsquigarrow \hat{l}'} \\
 \\
 \text{INDIRECT LOOKUP - KNOWN VERSION} \\
 \frac{\hat{g} = - \uplus \{ \hat{l}'' \mapsto_{V(p')} \hat{l} \} \quad p' \neq p \quad \hat{g}[\hat{l}'', p] \rightsquigarrow \hat{l}'}{\hat{g}[\hat{l}, p] \rightsquigarrow \hat{l}'} \\
 \\
 \text{INDIRECT LOOKUP - UNKNOWN VERSION} \\
 \frac{\hat{g} = - \uplus \{ \hat{l}'' \mapsto_{V(*)} \hat{l} \} \quad \hat{g}[\hat{l}'', p] \rightsquigarrow \hat{l}'}{\hat{g}[\hat{l}, p] \rightsquigarrow \hat{l}'} \\
 \\
 \text{PROPERTY LOOKUP} \\
 \hat{g}[\hat{l}, p] \triangleq \{ \hat{l}' \mid \hat{g}[\hat{l}, p] \rightsquigarrow \hat{l}' \}
 \end{array}$$

Definition A.2 (Abstract Expression Evaluation). Given an expression $e \in \mathcal{Exp}$ and an abstract store $\hat{\rho} \in \widehat{\mathcal{Sto}}$, the evaluation of e under $\hat{\rho}$, written $\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}}$ is formally defined as follows:

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \text{VALUE EVALUATION} \\
 \llbracket v \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}} \triangleq \{ \hat{l}_\bullet \} \\
 \\
 \text{VARIABLE EVALUATION} \\
 \llbracket x \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}} \triangleq \hat{\rho}(x)
 \end{array}$$

Where \hat{l}_\bullet is a fixed abstract location used to represent dependencies of literal values included in the program.

Definition A.3 (Original Version). Given an abstract MDG \hat{g} and an abstract location \hat{l} , the original version of \hat{l} in \hat{g} , written $\text{orig}(\hat{g}, \hat{l})$, is computed as follows:

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \text{BASE} \\
 \frac{\neg \exists \hat{l}'. \hat{l}' \mapsto_{V(-)} \hat{l} \in \hat{g}}{\text{orig}(\hat{g}, \hat{l}) \triangleq \hat{l}} \\
 \\
 \text{REC} \\
 \frac{\hat{l}' \mapsto_{V(-)} \hat{l} \in \hat{g} \quad \text{orig}(\hat{g}, \hat{l}') = \hat{l}''}{\text{orig}(\hat{g}, \hat{l}) \triangleq \hat{l}''}
 \end{array}$$

Definition A.4 (Abstract New Version).

$$\frac{\text{NEW VERSION - KNOWN PROPERTY - STRONG UPDATE}}{\hat{l}_i = \text{alloc}(\hat{g}, i) \quad \hat{g}' = \hat{g} \cup \hat{l} \mapsto_{V(p)} \hat{l}_i \quad \hat{\rho}' = \hat{\rho}[i/i]} \\ \text{NV}_i(\hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, \{\hat{l}\}, p) \triangleq (\hat{g}', \hat{\rho}', \hat{l}_i)$$

$$\frac{\text{NEW VERSION - KNOWN PROPERTY - WEAK UPDATE}}{\hat{l}_i = \text{alloc}(\hat{g}, i) \quad \hat{g}' = \hat{g} \cup \{\hat{l} \mapsto_{V(p)} \hat{l}_i \mid \hat{l} \in L\} \quad \hat{\rho}' = \hat{\rho}[i, \hat{l}_i/i \mid \hat{l} \in L]} \\ \text{NV}_i(\hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, L, p) \triangleq (\hat{g}', \hat{\rho}', \hat{l}_i)$$

$$\frac{\text{NEW VERSION - UNKNOWN PROPERTY - STRONG UPDATE}}{\hat{l}_i = \text{alloc}(\hat{g}, i) \quad \hat{g}' = \hat{g} \cup \hat{l} \mapsto_{V(*)} \hat{l}_i \cup \{\hat{l}_2 \mapsto_D \hat{l}_i \mid \hat{l}_2 \in L_2\} \quad \hat{\rho}' = \hat{\rho}[i/i]} \\ \text{NV}_i^*(\hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, \hat{l}, L_2) \triangleq (\hat{g}', \hat{\rho}', \hat{l}_i)$$

$$\frac{\text{NEW VERSION - UNKNOWN PROPERTY - WEAK UPDATE}}{\hat{l}_i = \text{alloc}(\hat{g}, i) \quad \hat{g}' = \hat{g} \cup \{\hat{l} \mapsto_{V(*)} \hat{l}_i \mid \hat{l} \in L\} \cup \{\hat{l}_2 \mapsto_D \hat{l}_i \mid \hat{l}_2 \in L_2\} \quad \hat{\rho}' = \hat{\rho}[i, \hat{l}_i/i \mid \hat{l} \in L]} \\ \text{NV}_i^*(\hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, L, L_2) \triangleq (\hat{g}', \hat{\rho}', \hat{l}_i)$$

Definition A.5 (Add Property).

$$\frac{\text{ADD KNOWN PROPERTY - BASE}}{\text{AP}_i(\hat{g}, \emptyset, p) \triangleq \hat{g}} \quad \frac{\text{ADD KNOWN PROPERTY - EXISTING}}{\text{orig}(\hat{g}, \hat{l}) = \hat{l}_1 \quad \exists \hat{l}_2. \hat{l}_1 \mapsto_{P(p)} \hat{l}_2 \in \hat{g}} \\ \text{AP}_i(\hat{g}, \{\hat{l}\} \uplus L, p) \triangleq \text{AP}_i(\hat{g}, L, p)$$

$$\frac{\text{ADD KNOWN PROPERTY - NON-EXISTING}}{\text{orig}(\hat{g}, \hat{l}) = \hat{l}_1 \quad \neg \exists \hat{l}_2. \hat{l}_1 \mapsto_{P(p)} \hat{l}_2 \in \hat{g} \quad \hat{l}_i = \text{alloc}(\hat{g}, i) \quad \hat{g}' = \hat{g} \uplus \hat{l}_1 \mapsto_{P(p)} \hat{l}_i} \\ \text{AP}_i(\hat{g}, \{\hat{l}\} \uplus L, p) \triangleq \text{AP}_i(\hat{g}', L, p)$$

$$\frac{\text{ADD UNKNOWN PROPERTY - BASE}}{\text{AP}_i^*(\hat{g}, \emptyset, L_2) \triangleq \hat{g}} \quad \frac{\text{ADD UNKNOWN PROPERTY - EXISTING}}{\text{orig}(\hat{g}, \hat{l}) = \hat{l}_1 \quad \exists \hat{l}'. \hat{l}_1 \mapsto_{P(*)} \hat{l}' \in \hat{g} \quad \hat{g}' = \hat{g} \cup \{\hat{l}_2 \mapsto_D \hat{l}' \mid \hat{l}_2 \in L_2\}} \\ \text{AP}_i^*(\hat{g}, \{\hat{l}\} \uplus L, L_2) \triangleq \text{AP}_i^*(\hat{g}, L, L_2)$$

$$\frac{\text{ADD UNKNOWN PROPERTY - NON-EXISTING}}{\text{orig}(\hat{g}, \hat{l}) = \hat{l}_1 \quad \neg \exists \hat{l}'. \hat{l}_1 \mapsto_{P(*)} \hat{l}' \in \hat{g} \quad \hat{l}_i = \text{alloc}(\hat{g}, i) \quad \hat{g}' = \hat{g} \cup \hat{l} \mapsto_{P(*)} \hat{l}_i \cup \{\hat{l}_2 \mapsto_D \hat{l}_i \mid \hat{l}_2 \in L_2\}} \\ \text{AP}_i^*(\hat{g}, \{\hat{l}\} \uplus L, L_2) \triangleq \text{AP}_i^*(\hat{g}', L, L_2)$$

A.3 Well-defined Analysis

Definition A.6 (Order Relation). Abstract MDGs and stores are ordered as follows:

- An abstract MDG $\hat{g}_1 = (\hat{V}_1, \hat{E}_1)$ is said to be lower than or equal to an abstract MDG $\hat{g}_2 = (\hat{V}_2, \hat{E}_2)$, written $\hat{g}_1 \sqsubseteq \hat{g}_2$, if and only if $\hat{E}_1 \subseteq \hat{E}_2$.
- An abstract store $\hat{\rho}_1 \in \widehat{\text{Sto}}$ is said to be lower than or equal to an abstract store $\hat{\rho}_2 \in \widehat{\text{Sto}}$, written $\hat{\rho}_1 \sqsubseteq \hat{\rho}_2$, if and only if:

$$\text{dom}(\hat{\rho}_1) \subseteq \text{dom}(\hat{\rho}_2) \wedge \forall x \in \text{dom}(\hat{\rho}_1). \hat{\rho}_1(x) \subseteq \hat{\rho}_2(x)$$

Notation: We use the notation $(\hat{g}_1, \hat{\rho}_1) \sqsubseteq (\hat{g}_2, \hat{\rho}_2)$ to mean that $\hat{g}_1 \sqsubseteq \hat{g}_2$ and $\hat{\rho}_1 \sqsubseteq \hat{\rho}_2$.

<p style="text-align: center;">ASSIGN-EXPR</p> $\frac{\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}} = L \quad \hat{\rho}' = \hat{\rho}[x \mapsto L]}{\mathcal{A}(x := e, \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}) \triangleq (\hat{g}, \hat{\rho}')}$	<p style="text-align: center;">ASSIGN-OP</p> $\frac{\llbracket e_j \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}} = L_j \mid_{j=1,2} \quad \hat{l}_i = \text{alloc}(\hat{g}, i)}{\hat{g}' = \hat{g} \uplus \{\hat{l} \mapsto_D \hat{l}_i \mid \hat{l} \in L_1 \cup L_2\}}{\mathcal{A}(x :=_i e_1 \oplus e_2, \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}) \triangleq (\hat{g}', \hat{\rho}[x \mapsto \{\hat{l}_i\}]}$
<p style="text-align: center;">NEW OBJECT</p> $\frac{\hat{l}_i = \text{alloc}(\hat{g}, i) \quad \hat{\rho}' = \hat{\rho}[x \mapsto \{\hat{l}_i\}]}{\hat{g}' = \text{AddNode}(\hat{g}, \hat{l}_i)}{\mathcal{A}(x := \{ \}^i, \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}) \triangleq (\hat{g}', \hat{\rho}')}$	<p style="text-align: center;">STATIC PROPERTY LOOKUP</p> $\frac{\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}} = L \quad \hat{g}' = \text{AP}_i(\hat{g}, L, p)}{L' = \{\hat{l}' \mid \hat{l} \in L \wedge \hat{l}' \in \hat{g}'[\hat{l}, p]\}}{\mathcal{A}(x :=_i e.p, \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}) \triangleq (\hat{g}', \hat{\rho}[x \mapsto L'])}$
<p style="text-align: center;">DYNAMIC PROPERTY LOOKUP</p> $\frac{\llbracket e_j \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}} = L_j \mid_{j=1,2} \quad \hat{g}' = \text{AP}_i^*(\hat{g}, L_1, L_2)}{L' = \{\hat{l}' \mid \hat{l} \in L_1 \wedge \hat{l}' \in \hat{g}'[\hat{l}, *]\}}{\mathcal{A}(x :=_i e_1[e_2], \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}) \triangleq (\hat{g}', \hat{\rho}[x \mapsto L'])}$	<p style="text-align: center;">STATIC PROPERTY UPDATE</p> $\frac{\llbracket e_j \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}} = L_j \mid_{j=1,2} \quad (\hat{g}'', \hat{\rho}', L'_1) = \text{NV}_i(\hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, L_1, p)}{\hat{g}' = \hat{g}'' \uplus \{\hat{l}_1 \mapsto_{\text{P}(p)} \hat{l}_2 \mid \hat{l}_1 \in L'_1 \wedge \hat{l}_2 \in L_2\}}{\mathcal{A}(e_1.p :=_i e_2, \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}) \triangleq (\hat{g}', \hat{\rho}')}$
<p style="text-align: center;">DYNAMIC PROPERTY UPDATE</p> $\frac{\llbracket e_j \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}} = L_j \mid_{j=1}^3 \quad (\hat{g}'', \hat{\rho}', L'_1) = \text{NV}_i^*(\hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, L_1, L_2)}{\hat{g}' = \hat{g}'' \uplus \{\hat{l}_1 \mapsto_{\text{P}(\ast)} \hat{l}_3 \mid \hat{l}_1 \in L'_1 \wedge \hat{l}_3 \in L_3\}}{\mathcal{A}(e_1[e_2] :=_i e_3, \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}) \triangleq (\hat{g}', \hat{\rho}')}$	<p style="text-align: center;">CALL</p> $\frac{\llbracket e_j \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}} = L_j \mid_{j=1}^n \quad (\hat{g}_0, \hat{\rho}_0) = (\hat{g}, \hat{\rho})}{(\hat{g}_j, \hat{l}_j) = \text{merge}(\hat{g}_{j-1}, L_j) \mid_{j=1}^n}{\text{body}(f) = \text{function}(x_1, \dots, x_n)\{s; \text{return } e\}}{\hat{\rho}'' = [x_j \mapsto \hat{l}_j \mid_{j=1}^n] \quad \mathcal{A}(s, \hat{g}_n, \hat{\rho}'') = (\hat{g}', \hat{\rho}''')}{\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}'''} = L_r \quad \hat{\rho}' = \hat{\rho}[x \mapsto L_r]}{\mathcal{A}(x := f(e_1, \dots, e_n), \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}) \triangleq (\hat{g}', \hat{\rho}')}$
<p style="text-align: center;">IF STATEMENT</p> $\frac{\mathcal{A}(s_j, \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}) = (\hat{g}_j, \hat{\rho}_j) \mid_{j=1}^2}{\mathcal{A}(\text{if}(e)\{s_1\} \text{ else } \{s_2\}, \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}) \triangleq (\hat{g}_1 \sqcup \hat{g}_2, \hat{\rho}_1 \sqcup \hat{\rho}_2)}$	<p style="text-align: center;">SEQUENCE</p> $\frac{\mathcal{A}(s_1, \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}) = (\hat{g}_1, \hat{\rho}_1) \quad \mathcal{A}(s_2, \hat{g}_1, \hat{\rho}_1) = (\hat{g}', \hat{\rho}')}{\mathcal{A}(s_1; s_2, \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}) \triangleq (\hat{g}', \hat{\rho}')}$
<p style="text-align: center;">WHILE</p> $\frac{\text{Ifp}(\mathcal{A}(s))(\hat{g}, \hat{\rho}) = (\hat{g}', \hat{\rho}')}{\mathcal{A}(\text{while}(e)\{s\}, \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}) \triangleq \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}'}$	

Fig. 1. Selected Graph Construction Analysis: $\mathcal{A}(\hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, s) \triangleq \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}'$.

Remark (Abstract Domain - Lattice Structure).

- Abstract MDGs form a lattice under \sqsubseteq , with the *least upper bound (lub)* and *greatest lower bound (glb)* defined as follows:

$$(\hat{V}_1, \hat{E}_1) \sqcup (\hat{V}_2, \hat{E}_2) \triangleq (\hat{V}_1 \cup \hat{V}_2, \hat{E}_1 \cup \hat{E}_2)$$

$$(\hat{V}_1, \hat{E}_1) \sqcap (\hat{V}_2, \hat{E}_2) \triangleq (\hat{V}_1 \cap \hat{V}_2, \hat{E}_1 \cap \hat{E}_2)$$

- Abstract stores form a lattice under \sqsubseteq , with the *least upper bound (lub)* and *greatest lower bound (glb)* defined as follows:

$$(\hat{\rho}_1 \sqcup \hat{\rho}_2)(x) = \begin{cases} \hat{\rho}_1(x) \cup \hat{\rho}_2(x) & \text{if } x \in \text{dom}(\hat{\rho}_1) \cap \text{dom}(\hat{\rho}_2) \\ \hat{\rho}_1(x) & \text{if } x \in \text{dom}(\hat{\rho}_1) \wedge x \notin \text{dom}(\hat{\rho}_2) \\ \hat{\rho}_2(x) & \text{if } x \notin \text{dom}(\hat{\rho}_1) \wedge x \in \text{dom}(\hat{\rho}_2) \\ \perp & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$(\hat{\rho}_1 \sqcap \hat{\rho}_2)(x) = \begin{cases} \hat{\rho}_1(x) \cap \hat{\rho}_2(x) & \text{if } x \in \text{dom}(\hat{\rho}_1) \cap \text{dom}(\hat{\rho}_2) \\ \perp & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

LEMMA A.7 (MONOTONICITY). *For any abstract MDGs \hat{g}_1 and \hat{g}_2 , abstract stores $\hat{\rho}_1$ and $\hat{\rho}_2$, and statement s , it holds that:*

$$\mathcal{A}(\hat{g}_1, \hat{\rho}_1, s) = \hat{g}_2, \hat{\rho}_2 \implies \hat{g}_1 \sqsubseteq \hat{g}_2 \quad (1)$$

$$(\hat{g}_1, \hat{\rho}_1) \sqsubseteq (\hat{g}_2, \hat{\rho}_2) \implies \mathcal{A}(\hat{g}_1, \hat{\rho}_1, s) \sqsubseteq \mathcal{A}(\hat{g}_2, \hat{\rho}_2, s) \quad (2)$$

PROOF. The proof of Property 1 goes by induction on the derivation of $\mathcal{A}(\hat{g}_1, \hat{\rho}_1, s) = \hat{g}_2, \hat{\rho}_2$. It suffices to note that none of the rules of the analysis removes edges from the graph; hence, the edges of the input graph are always contained in the edges of the output graph.

The proof of Property 2 also goes by induction on the derivation of $\mathcal{A}(\hat{g}_1, \hat{\rho}_1, s)$. The argument is more subtle than that of Property 1 given that abstract stores do not observe the equivalent of Property 1; i.e., the implication $\mathcal{A}(\hat{g}_1, \hat{\rho}_1, s) = \hat{g}_2, \hat{\rho}_2 \implies \hat{\rho}_1 \sqsubseteq \hat{\rho}_2$ does not hold in general. The proof is based on the Expression Evaluation Monotonicity Lemma (Lemma A.8). \square

LEMMA A.8 (EXPRESSION EVALUATION MONOTONICITY). *For every abstract stores $\hat{\rho}_1$ and $\hat{\rho}_2$, it holds that:*

$$\hat{\rho}_1 \sqsubseteq \hat{\rho}_2 \implies \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}_1} \sqsubseteq \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}_2}$$

PROOF. [CASE 1] $e = v$. From definition, we know that $\llbracket v \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}} \triangleq \{l_\bullet\}$. It follows that:

$$\llbracket v \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}_1} = \{l_\bullet\} \subseteq \{l_\bullet\} = \llbracket v \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}_2}$$

[CASE 2] $e = x$. From definition, we know that $\llbracket x \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}} \triangleq \hat{\rho}(x)$. It follows that:

$$\llbracket x \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}_1} = \hat{\rho}_1(x) \subseteq \hat{\rho}_2(x) = \llbracket x \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}_2}$$

\square

LEMMA A.9 (FIXED-POINT COMPUTATION). *Let $\mathcal{F} : (\hat{\mathcal{G}} \times \widehat{\text{Sto}}) \rightarrow (\hat{\mathcal{G}} \times \widehat{\text{Sto}})$, be a monotone functional on abstract states satisfying the property: $\mathcal{F}(\hat{g}_1, \hat{\rho}_1) = (\hat{g}_2, \hat{\rho}_2) \implies \hat{g}_1 \sqsubseteq \hat{g}_2$. Then, given a graph \hat{g} and store $\hat{\rho}$, the least fixed point of \mathcal{F} greater than or equal to $(\hat{g}, \hat{\rho})$ is given by the following rules:*

$\frac{\text{BASE CASE}}{\mathcal{F}(\hat{g}, \hat{\rho}) = (\hat{g}, \hat{\rho})}$	$\frac{\text{RECURSIVE CASE}}{\mathcal{F}(\hat{g}, \hat{\rho}) = (\hat{g}', \hat{\rho}') \quad \text{Ifp}(\mathcal{F})(\hat{g}', \hat{\rho} \sqcup \hat{\rho}') = (\hat{g}'', \hat{\rho}'')}$
$\frac{}{\text{Ifp}(\mathcal{F})(\hat{g}, \hat{\rho}) \triangleq (\hat{g}, \hat{\rho})}$	$\frac{}{\text{Ifp}(\mathcal{F})(\hat{g}, \hat{\rho}) \triangleq (\hat{g}'', \hat{\rho}'')}$

A.4 Instrumented Semantics

Definition A.10 (Concrete Graph Property Lookup). Given a concrete graph g , a location l , and a property p , the graph lookup operation on g and l , written $g[l, p]$, is formally defined as follows:

$\frac{\text{DIRECT LOOKUP - BASE CASE}}{g = - \uplus \{l \mapsto_{\text{P}(p)} l'\}}$	$\frac{\text{INDIRECT LOOKUP - RECURSIVE CASE}}{g = - \uplus \{l'' \mapsto_{\text{V}(p')} l\} \quad p' \neq p \quad g[l'', p] = l'}$
$\frac{}{g[l, p] \triangleq l'}$	$\frac{}{g[l, p] \triangleq l'}$

Definition A.11 (Concrete Expression Evaluation). Given an expression $e \in \text{Exp}$ and a concrete store $\rho \in \text{Sto}$, the evaluation of e under ρ , written $\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\rho}$ is formally defined as follows:

$\frac{\text{VALUE EVALUATION}}{\llbracket v_i \rrbracket_{\rho} = l_i}$	$\frac{\text{VARIABLE EVALUATION}}{\llbracket x \rrbracket_{\rho} = \rho(x)}$
--	---

Where l_i is a concrete location that stores a value v_i .

<p>ASSIGN-EXPR</p> $\frac{\llbracket e \rrbracket_\rho = l \quad \rho' = \rho[x \mapsto l]}{\langle g, h, \rho, x := e \rangle \Downarrow_c \langle g, h, \rho' \rangle}$	<p>ASSIGN-OP</p> $\frac{\llbracket e_i \rrbracket_\rho = l_i \mid_{i=1,2} \quad l \text{ fresh} \quad g' = g \uplus \{l_i \mapsto_D l \mid_{i=1}^2\} \quad h' = h[l \mapsto \oplus(h(l_1), h(l_2))]}{\langle g, h, \rho, x := e_1 \oplus e_2 \rangle \Downarrow_c \langle g', h', \rho' \rangle}$
<p>STATIC PROPERTY LOOKUP</p> $\frac{\llbracket e \rrbracket_\rho = l \quad g[l, p] = l' \quad \rho' = \rho[x \mapsto l']}{\langle g, h, \rho, x := e.p \rangle \Downarrow_c \langle g, h, \rho' \rangle}$	<p>DYNAMIC PROPERTY LOOKUP</p> $\frac{\llbracket e_i \rrbracket_\rho = l_i \mid_{i=1}^2 \quad p = h(l_2) \quad g[l_1, p] = l' \quad \rho' = \rho[x \mapsto l'] \quad g' = g \uplus \{l_2 \mapsto_D l'\}}{\langle g, h, \rho, x := e_1[e_2] \rangle \Downarrow_c \langle g', h, \rho' \rangle}$
<p>STATIC PROPERTY UPDATE</p> $\frac{\llbracket e_i \rrbracket_\rho = l_i \mid_{i=1,2} \quad (g'', \rho', l') = \text{NV}_c(g, \rho, l_1, p) \quad g' = g'' \uplus \{l' \mapsto_{P(p)} l_2\}}{\langle g, h, \rho, e_1.p := e_2 \rangle \Downarrow_c \langle g', h, \rho' \rangle}$	<p>DYNAMIC PROPERTY UPDATE</p> $\frac{\llbracket e_i \rrbracket_\rho = l_i \mid_{i=1}^3 \quad p = h(l_2) \quad (g'', \rho', l'_1) = \text{NV}_c(g, \rho, l_1, l_2, p) \quad g' = g'' \uplus \{l'_1 \mapsto_{P(p)} l_3\}}{\langle g, h, \rho, e_1[e_2] := e_3 \rangle \Downarrow_c \langle g', h, \rho' \rangle}$
<p>NEW OBJECT</p> $\frac{l \text{ fresh} \quad g' = \text{AddNode}(g, l) \quad \rho' = \rho[x \mapsto l]}{\langle g, h, \rho, x := \{\} \rangle \Downarrow_c \langle g', h, \rho' \rangle}$	<p>SEQUENCE</p> $\frac{\langle g, h, \rho, s_1 \rangle \Downarrow_c \langle g_1, h_1, \rho_1 \rangle \quad \langle g_1, h_1, \rho_1, s_2 \rangle \Downarrow_c \langle g', h', \rho' \rangle}{\langle g, h, \rho, s_1; s_2 \rangle \Downarrow_c \langle g', h', \rho' \rangle}$
<p>CALL</p> $\frac{\llbracket e_i \rrbracket_\rho = l_i \mid_{i=1}^n \quad \text{body}(f) = \text{function}(x_1, \dots, x_n)\{s; \text{return } e\} \quad \rho'' = [x_i \mapsto l_i \mid_{i=1}^n] \quad \langle g, h, \rho'', s \rangle \Downarrow_c \langle g', h', \rho'' \rangle \quad \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\rho''} = l_r \quad \rho' = \rho[x \mapsto l_r]}{\langle g, h, \rho, x := f(e_1, \dots, e_n) \rangle \Downarrow_c \langle g', h', \rho' \rangle}$	
<p>IF - TRUE</p> $\frac{h(\llbracket e \rrbracket_\rho) = \text{true} \quad \langle g, h, \rho, s_1 \rangle \Downarrow_c \langle g', h', \rho' \rangle}{\langle g, h, \rho, \text{if}(e_1)\{s_1\} \text{ else } \{s_2\}\rangle \Downarrow_c \langle g', h', \rho' \rangle}$	<p>IF - FALSE</p> $\frac{h(\llbracket e \rrbracket_\rho) = \text{false} \quad \langle g, h, \rho, s_2 \rangle \Downarrow_c \langle g', h', \rho' \rangle}{\langle g, h, \rho, \text{if}(e_1)\{s_1\} \text{ else } \{s_2\}\rangle \Downarrow_c \langle g', h', \rho' \rangle}$
<p>WHILE - FALSE</p> $\frac{h(\llbracket e \rrbracket_\rho) = \text{false}}{\langle g, h, \rho, \text{while}(e)\{s\}\rangle \Downarrow_c \langle g, h, \rho \rangle}$	<p>WHILE - TRUE</p> $\frac{h(\llbracket e \rrbracket_\rho) = \text{false} \quad \langle g, h, \rho, s \rangle \Downarrow_c \langle g', h', \rho' \rangle \quad \langle g', h', \rho', \text{while}(e)\{s\}\rangle \Downarrow_c \langle g'', h'', \rho'' \rangle}{\langle g, h, \rho, \text{while}(e)\{s\}\rangle \Downarrow_c \langle g'', h'', \rho'' \rangle}$

Fig. 2. Instrumented Semantics

Definition A.12 (Concrete New Version Auxiliary Function).

$$\frac{\text{DYNAMIC NEW VERSION} \quad l' \text{ fresh} \quad g' = g \cup l \mapsto_{V(p)} l' \cup l_p \mapsto_D l' \quad \rho' = \rho[l'/l]}{\text{NV}_c(g, \rho, l, l_p, p) \triangleq (g', \rho', l')}$$

$$\frac{\text{STATIC NEW VERSION} \quad l' \text{ fresh} \quad g' = g \cup l \mapsto_{V(p)} l' \quad \rho' = \rho[l'/l]}{\text{NV}_c(g, \rho, l, p) \triangleq (g', \rho', l')}$$

$\frac{\text{ASSIGN-EXPR} \quad \frac{\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}} = L \quad \hat{\rho}' = \hat{\rho}[x \mapsto L]}{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, x := e \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}' \rangle}}{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, x := e \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}' \rangle}$	$\frac{\text{ASSIGN-OP} \quad \frac{\llbracket e_j \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}} = L_j \mid_{j=1,2} \quad \hat{l}_i = \text{alloc}(\hat{g}, i) \quad \hat{g}' = \hat{g} \uplus \{ \hat{l} \mapsto_{\text{D}} \hat{l}_i \mid \hat{l} \in L_1 \cup L_2 \}}{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, x :=_i e_1 \oplus e_2 \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}[x \mapsto \{ \hat{l}_i \}] \rangle}}{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, x :=_i e_1 \oplus e_2 \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}[x \mapsto \{ \hat{l}_i \}] \rangle}$
$\frac{\text{STATIC PROPERTY LOOKUP} \quad \frac{\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}} = L \quad \hat{g}' = \text{AP}_i(\hat{g}, L, p) \quad L' = \{ \hat{l}' \mid \hat{l} \in L \wedge \hat{l}' \in \hat{g}'[\hat{l}, p] \}}{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, x :=_i e.p \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}[x \mapsto L'] \rangle}}{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, x :=_i e.p \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}[x \mapsto L'] \rangle}$	$\frac{\text{DYNAMIC PROPERTY LOOKUP} \quad \frac{\llbracket e_j \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}} = L_j \mid_{j=1,2} \quad \hat{g}' = \text{AP}_i^*(\hat{g}, L_1, L_2) \quad L' = \{ \hat{l}' \mid \hat{l} \in L_1 \wedge \hat{l}' \in \hat{g}'[\hat{l}, *] \}}{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, x :=_i e_1[e_2] \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}[x \mapsto L'] \rangle}}{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, x :=_i e_1[e_2] \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}[x \mapsto L'] \rangle}$
$\frac{\text{STATIC PROPERTY UPDATE} \quad \frac{\llbracket e_j \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}} = L_j \mid_{j=i}^2 \quad (\hat{g}'', \hat{\rho}', L'_1) = \text{NV}_i(\hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, L_1, p) \quad \hat{g}' = \hat{g}'' \uplus \{ \hat{l}_1 \mapsto_{\text{P}(p)} \hat{l}_2 \mid \hat{l}_1 \in L'_1 \wedge \hat{l}_2 \in L_2 \}}{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, e_1.p :=_i e_2 \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \rangle}}{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, e_1.p :=_i e_2 \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \rangle}$	$\frac{\text{DYNAMIC PROPERTY UPDATE} \quad \frac{\llbracket e_j \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}} = L_j \mid_{j=1}^3 \quad (\hat{g}'', \hat{\rho}', L'_1) = \text{NV}_i^*(\hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, L_1, L_2) \quad \hat{g}' = \hat{g}'' \uplus \{ \hat{l}_1 \mapsto_{\text{P}(*)} \hat{l}_3 \mid \hat{l}_1 \in L'_1 \wedge \hat{l}_3 \in L_3 \}}{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, e_1[e_2] :=_i e_3 \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \rangle}}{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, e_1[e_2] :=_i e_3 \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \rangle}$
$\frac{\text{NEW OBJECT} \quad \frac{\hat{l}_i = \text{alloc}(\hat{g}, i) \quad \hat{\rho}' = \hat{\rho}[x \mapsto \{ \hat{l}_i \}] \quad \hat{g}' = \text{AddNode}(\hat{g}, \hat{l}_i)}{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, x := \{ \}^i \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \rangle}}{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, x := \{ \}^i \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \rangle}$	$\frac{\text{CALL} \quad \frac{\llbracket e_j \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}} = L_j \mid_{j=1}^n \quad (\hat{g}_0, \hat{\rho}_0) = (\hat{g}, \hat{\rho}) \quad (\hat{g}_j, \hat{l}_j) = \text{merge}(\hat{g}_{j-1}, L_j) \mid_{j=1}^n \quad \text{body}(f) = \text{function}(x_1, \dots, x_n) \{ s; \text{return } e \} \quad \hat{\rho}'' = [x_j \mapsto \hat{l}_j \mid_{j=1}^n] \langle \hat{g}_n, \hat{\rho}'', s \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}''' \rangle \quad \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}'''} = L_r \quad \hat{\rho}' = \hat{\rho}[x \mapsto L_r]}{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, x := f(e_1, \dots, e_n) \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \rangle}}{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, x := f(e_1, \dots, e_n) \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \rangle}$
$\frac{\text{IF STATEMENT} \quad \frac{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, s_1 \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}_1, \hat{\rho}_1 \rangle \mid_{i=1}^2}{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, \text{if}(e) \{ s_1 \} \text{ else } \{ s_2 \} \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}_1 \sqcup \hat{g}_2, \hat{\rho}_1 \sqcup \hat{\rho}_2 \rangle}}{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, \text{if}(e) \{ s_1 \} \text{ else } \{ s_2 \} \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}_1 \sqcup \hat{g}_2, \hat{\rho}_1 \sqcup \hat{\rho}_2 \rangle}$	$\frac{\text{SEQUENCE} \quad \frac{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, s_1 \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}_1, \hat{\rho}_1 \rangle \quad \langle \hat{g}_1, \hat{\rho}_1, s_2 \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \rangle}{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, s_1; s_2 \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \rangle}}{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, s_1; s_2 \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \rangle}$
$\frac{\text{WHILE} \quad \frac{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, s \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho} \rangle}{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, \text{while}(e) \{ s \} \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho} \rangle}}{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, \text{while}(e) \{ s \} \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho} \rangle}$	$\frac{\text{WEAKENING} \quad \frac{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho} \rangle \sqsubseteq \langle \hat{g}_1, \hat{\rho}_1 \rangle \quad \langle \hat{g}_1, \hat{\rho}_1, s \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}_2, \hat{\rho}_2 \rangle \quad \langle \hat{g}_2, \hat{\rho}_2 \rangle \sqsubseteq \langle \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \rangle}{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, s \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \rangle}}{\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, s \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \rangle}$

 Fig. 3. Graph Construction Analysis (Declarative Spec): $\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, s \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \rangle$

A.5 Abstract Graph - Declarative Specification

LEMMA A.13 (ANALYSIS: ALGORITHMIC VERSION VS DECLARATIVE SPECIFICATION). *For any abstract MDGs \hat{g} and \hat{g}' , stores $\hat{\rho}$ and $\hat{\rho}'$, and statement $s \in \text{Stm}$, it holds that:*

$$\mathcal{A}(\hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, s) = \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \implies \langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, s \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \rangle$$

B SOUNDNESS (FULL KNOWLEDGE)

B.1 Main Definitions

Definition B.1 (MDGs Over-Approximation). An abstract MDG \hat{g} is said to over-approximate a concrete MDG g via abstraction function α , written $\hat{g} \sim_{\alpha} g$, if and only if the following hold:

- $\forall l_1, l_2 . l_1 \mapsto_{\text{D}} l_2 \in g \implies \alpha(l_1 \mapsto_{\text{D}} l_2) \in \hat{g}$
- $\forall l_1, l_2, p . l_1 \mapsto_{\text{P}(p)} l_2 \in g \implies \alpha(l_1 \mapsto_{\text{P}(p)} l_2) \in \hat{g} \vee \alpha(l_1 \mapsto_{\text{P}(*)} l_2) \in \hat{g}$

$$\bullet \forall l_1, l_2, p . l_1 \mapsto_{V(p)} l_2 \in g \implies \alpha(l_1 \mapsto_{V(p)} l_2) \in \hat{g} \vee \alpha(l_1 \mapsto_{V(*)} l_2) \in \hat{g}$$

Where $\alpha(l_1 \mapsto_{\tau} l_2) \equiv \alpha(l_1) \mapsto_{\tau} \alpha(l_2)$.

Definition B.2 (Store Over-Approximation). An abstract store $\hat{\rho}$ is said to over-approximate a concrete store ρ via abstraction function α , written $\hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha} \rho$, iff: $\forall x \in \text{dom}(\rho) . \alpha(\rho(x)) \in \hat{\rho}(x)$.

Definition B.3 (State Over-Approximation). An abstract state $(\hat{g}, \hat{\rho})$ is said to over-approximate a concrete state (g, ρ) , written $\hat{g}, \hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha} g, \rho$, if $\hat{g} \sim_{\alpha} g$ and $\hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha} \rho$.

B.2 Auxiliary Results

LEMMA B.4 (EXPRESSION EVALUATION LEMMA). *For every abstract store $\hat{\rho}$, concrete store ρ , and abstraction function α , it holds that:*

$$\hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha} \rho \implies \exists \alpha' . \alpha' \geq \alpha \wedge \alpha'(\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\rho}) \in \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}}$$

PROOF. [CASE 1] $e = v$ (H1). Let $\alpha' = \alpha[l_i \mapsto l_{\bullet}]$ (H2). It follows that:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha'(\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\rho}) &= \alpha'(l_i) && \text{by H1 + A.11} \\ &= l_{\bullet} && \text{by H2} \\ &\in \{l_{\bullet}\} = \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}} && \text{by A.2 + H1} \end{aligned}$$

[CASE 2] $e = x$ (H1). Let $\alpha' = \alpha$ (H2). It follows that:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha'(\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\rho}) &= \alpha(\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\rho}) && \text{by H2} \\ &= \alpha(\rho(x)) && \text{by H1 + A.11} \\ &\in \hat{\rho}(x) = \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}} && \text{by H1 + A.2 + B.2} \end{aligned}$$

□

LEMMA B.5 (α -EXTENSION LEMMA). *For every abstract graph \hat{g} , abstract store $\hat{\rho}$, concrete graph g , concrete store ρ , and abstraction functions α and α' , such that $\hat{g}, \hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha} g, \rho$ and $\alpha' \geq \alpha$, it holds that $\hat{g}, \hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha'} g, \rho$.*

PROOF. Assume that $\hat{\rho}, \hat{g} \sim_{\alpha} \rho, g$ (H1), and $\alpha' \geq \alpha$ (H2). We want to prove that:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha'(\rho(x)) &\in \hat{\rho}(x) && \text{(I1)} \\ \forall l_1, l_2, \tau . l_1 \mapsto_{\tau} l_2 \in g &\implies \alpha'(l_1 \mapsto_{\tau} l_2) \subseteq \hat{g} && \text{(I2)} \end{aligned}$$

Take $x \in \text{dom}(\rho)$. The proof of I1 goes as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha'(\rho(x)) &= \alpha(\rho(x)) && \text{by } \rho(x) \in \text{dom}(\alpha) + \text{H2} \\ &\subseteq \hat{\rho}(x) && \text{by definition} \end{aligned}$$

The proof of I2 goes as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} l_1 \mapsto_{\tau} l_2 \in g &\implies \alpha(l_1 \mapsto_{\tau} l_2) \in \hat{g} && \text{by definition} \\ &\implies \alpha'(l_1 \mapsto_{\tau} l_2) \in \hat{g} && \text{by H2} \end{aligned}$$

Combining I1 and I2, it follows that $\hat{\rho}, \hat{g} \sim_{\alpha'} \rho, g$, establishing the result. □

LEMMA B.6 (STORE UPDATE LEMMA). *For every abstract store $\hat{\rho}$, concrete store ρ , variable x , set of locations L , location l , and abstraction function α , such that $\hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha} \rho$ and $\alpha(l) \in L$, it holds that $\hat{\rho}[x \mapsto L] \sim_{\alpha} \rho[x \mapsto l]$.*

PROOF. Assume that $\hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha} \rho$ (**H1**), $\hat{\rho}' = \hat{\rho}[x \mapsto L]$ (**H2**), $\rho' = \rho[x \mapsto L]$ (**H3**), and $\alpha(l) \in L$ (**H4**). We want to prove that:

$$\forall y \in \text{dom}(\rho') . \alpha(\rho'(y)) \in \hat{\rho}'(y) \text{ (I1)}$$

[CASE 1] $x \neq y$ (**H5**). The proof of **I1** goes as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha(\rho'(y)) &= \alpha(\rho(y)) && \text{by H3 + H5} \\ &\in \hat{\rho}(y) && \text{by H1} \\ &= \hat{\rho}'(y) && \text{by H2 + H5} \end{aligned}$$

[CASE 2] $x = y$ (**H5**). The proof of **I1** goes as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha(\rho'(y)) &= \alpha(\rho'(x)) && \text{by H5} \\ &= \alpha(l) && \text{by H3} \\ &\in L && \text{by H4} \\ &= \rho'(y) && \text{by H2 + H5} \end{aligned}$$

From **I1**, **H2**, and **H3**, it follows that:

- **I2** $\hat{\rho}' \sim_{\alpha} \rho'$

Equation **I2** establishes the result. □

LEMMA B.7 (CORRECTNESS PRESERVATION FOR GRAPH UNION). *For every abstract graphs \hat{g} and \hat{g}' , concrete graphs g and g' , and abstraction function α , such that: $\hat{g} \sim_{\alpha} g$ and $\hat{g}' \sim_{\alpha} g'$; it holds that: $\hat{g} \cup \hat{g}' \sim_{\alpha} g \cup g'$.*

LEMMA B.8 (STATIC NEW VERSION LEMMA). *For every abstract graphs \hat{g} and \hat{g}' , abstract stores $\hat{\rho}$ and $\hat{\rho}'$, concrete graph g and g' , concrete store ρ and ρ' , sets of locations L and L' , locations l and l' , property p , and index i , such that:*

- $\hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha} \rho$,
- $(\hat{g}', \hat{\rho}', L') = \text{NV}_i(\hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, L, p)$,
- $(g', \rho', l') = \text{NV}_c(g, \rho, l, p)$, and
- $\alpha(l) \in L$

Then, there is an abstraction function $\alpha' : \mathcal{L} \rightarrow \mathcal{L}$ such that: (1) $\alpha' \geq \alpha$, (2) $\hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \sim_{\alpha'} g', \rho'$, and (3) $\alpha'(l') \in L'$.

PROOF. Assume that $\hat{g}, \hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha} g, \rho$ (**H1**), $(\hat{g}', \hat{\rho}', L') = \text{NV}_i(\hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, L, p)$ (**H2**), $(g', \rho', l') = \text{NV}_c(g, \rho, l, p)$ (**H3**), and $\alpha(l) \in L$ (**H4**). We consider the two cases from Definition A.4.

[WEAK UPDATE] $|L| > 1$. From **H2**, it follows that:

- **I1.1:** $\hat{g}' = \hat{g} \cup \{\hat{l} \mapsto_{V(p)} \hat{l}_i \mid \hat{l} \in L\}$
- **I1.2:** $\hat{\rho}' = \hat{\rho}[\hat{i}_i, \hat{i}]/\hat{i} \mid \hat{l} \in L]$
- **I1.3:** $L' = \{\hat{l}_i\}$

Where $\hat{l}_i = \text{alloc}(\hat{g}, i)$. By **H3**, we conclude that:

- **I2.1:** $g' = g \uplus l \mapsto_{V(p)} l'$
- **I2.2:** $\rho' = \rho[l'/i]$
- **I2.3:** l' fresh

In the following, let:

- **I3.1:** $\hat{l}_0 = \alpha(l)$
- **I3.2:** $\alpha' = \alpha[l' \mapsto \hat{l}_i]$

It follows that:

- **I4.1:** $\alpha' \geq \alpha$
- **I4.2:** $\alpha'(l \mapsto_{V(p)} l') = \hat{l}_0 \mapsto_{V(p)} \hat{l}_i$

Applying the α -Extension Lemma (Lemma B.5) to **H1** and **I4.1**, we conclude that:

- **I5.1:** $\alpha'(g) \subseteq \hat{g}$
- **I5.2:** $\hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha'} \rho$

Combining **I4.2**, **I3.1**, and **H4**, it follows that:

- **I6:** $\alpha'(l \mapsto_{V(p)} l') \subseteq \{ \hat{l} \mapsto_{V(p)} \hat{l}_i \mid \hat{l} \in L \}$

Applying the Correctness Preservation for Graph Union (Lemma B.7) to **I5.1**, **I6**, **I1.1** and **I2.1**, we have that:

- **I7:** $\alpha'(g') \subseteq \hat{g}'$

It remains to prove that $\hat{\rho}' \sim_{\alpha'} \rho'$ (**I8**).

[CASE 1] $\rho'(x) = \rho(x)$ (**H5**). The proof of **I8** goes as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha'(\rho'(x)) &= \alpha'(\rho(x)) && \text{by H5} \\ &\in \hat{\rho}(x) && \text{by I5.2} \\ &\subseteq \hat{\rho}'(x) && \text{by I1.2} \end{aligned}$$

[CASE 2] $\rho'(x) \neq \rho(x)$ (**H5**). From **H5** and **I2.2**, it follows that:

- **I9:** $\rho'(x) = l' \wedge \rho(x) = l$

From **I9**, it follows that:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(x) = l &\implies \alpha(l) \in \hat{\rho}(x) && \text{by H1} \\ &\implies \hat{l}_0 \in \hat{\rho}(x) && \text{by I3.1} \\ &\implies \hat{l}_i \in \hat{\rho}'(x) && \text{by I1.2} \quad \text{(I10)} \end{aligned}$$

The proof of **I8** goes as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha'(\rho'(x)) &= \alpha'(l') && \text{by H5 + I9} \\ &= \hat{l}_i && \text{by I3.2} \\ &\subseteq \hat{\rho}'(x) && \text{by I10} \end{aligned}$$

Equations **I7** and **I8** establish the result.

[STRONG UPDATE] $L = \{\hat{l}\}$. From **H2**, it follows that:

- **I1.1:** $\hat{g}' = \hat{g} \uplus \hat{l} \mapsto_{V(p)} \hat{l}_i$
- **I1.2:** $\hat{\rho}' = \hat{\rho}[i/i]$
- **I1.3:** $L' = \{\hat{l}_i\}$

Where $\hat{l}_i = \text{alloc}(\hat{g}, i)$. By **H3**, we conclude that:

- **I2.1:** $g' = g \uplus l \mapsto_{V(p)} l'$
- **I2.2:** $\rho' = \rho[l'/l]$
- **I2.3:** l' fresh

By **H4**, we conclude that:

- **I3:** $\hat{l} = \alpha(l)$

In the following, take $\alpha' = \alpha[l' \mapsto \hat{l}_i]$ (**I4**), it follows that:

- **I5.1:** $\alpha' \geq \alpha$
- **I5.2:** $\alpha'(l \mapsto_{V(p)} l') = \hat{l} \mapsto_{V(p)} \hat{l}_i$

Applying the α -Extension Lemma (Lemma B.5) to **H1** and **I5.1**, we conclude that:

- **I6.1:** $\alpha'(g) \subseteq \hat{g}$
- **I6.2:** $\hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha'} \rho$

Combining **I6.1**, **I5.2**, **I2.1**, and **1.1**, it follows that:

- **I7:** $\alpha'(g') \subseteq \hat{g}'$

Applying the Store Substitution Lemma (Lemma B.12) to **I1.2**, **I2.2**, **I3**, **I4**, and **I6.2**, it follows that:

- **I8:** $\hat{\rho}' \sim_{\alpha'} \rho'$

Combining **I1.3** and **I4**, we conclude that:

- **I9:** $\alpha'(l') \in \{\hat{l}_i\} = L'$

Equations **I5.1**, **I7**, **I8**, and **9** establish the result. \square

LEMMA B.9 (PROPERTY LOOKUP LEMMA). *For every abstract graph \hat{g} , concrete graph g , locations l and l' , and property p , such that $\hat{g}, \hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha} g, \rho$ and $g[l, p] = l'$, it holds that $\alpha(l') \in \hat{g}[\alpha(l), p]$.*

PROOF. Assume that $\hat{g}, \hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha} g, \rho$ (**H1**), and $g[l, p] = l'$ (**H2**). We proceed by induction on the derivation of $g[l, p] = l'$.

[RECURSIVE CASE] $g[l, p] = l'$ was derived using the rule *Indirect Lookup* (Definition A.10). It follows that:

- **I1.1:** $g = - \uplus \{l'' \mapsto_{V(p')} l\}$
- **I1.2:** $p' \neq p$
- **I1.3:** $g[l'', p] = l'$

From **H1** and **I1.1**, it follows that:

- **I2:** $\hat{g} = - \uplus \{\alpha(l'') \mapsto_{V(p')} \alpha(l)\}$

Applying the induction hypothesis to **H1** and **I1.3**, it follows that:

- **I3:** $\alpha(l') \in \hat{g}[\alpha(l''), p] \equiv \hat{g}[\alpha(l''), p] \rightsquigarrow \alpha(l')$

Combining **I3**, **I1.2** and **I2**, we conclude:

- **I4:** $\hat{g}[\alpha(l), p] \rightsquigarrow \alpha(l') \equiv \alpha(l') \in \hat{g}[\alpha(l), p]$

I4 establishes the result.

[BASE CASE] $g[l, p] = l'$ was derived using the rule *Direct Lookup* (Definition A.10). It follows that:

- **I1:** $g = (l \mapsto_{P(p)} l') \uplus g'$

By **H1** and **I1**:

- **I2:** $\hat{g} = - \uplus \alpha(l) \mapsto_{P(p)} \alpha(l')$

From **I2**, it follows that:

- **I3:** $\hat{g}[\alpha(l), p] \rightsquigarrow \alpha(l') \equiv \alpha(l') \in \hat{g}[\alpha(l), p]$

I3 establishes the result. \square

LEMMA B.10 (ADD PROPERTY MONOTONICITY LEMMA). *For every abstract graphs \hat{g} and \hat{g}' , set of locations L , property p , and index i , such that $\text{AP}_i(\hat{g}, L, p) = \hat{g}'$, it holds that $\hat{g} \subseteq \hat{g}'$.*

PROOF. It suffices to note that the rules [STATIC PROPERTY UPDATE] and [DYNAMIC PROPERTY UPDATE] only extend the given graph. \square

LEMMA B.11 (ADD PROPERTY PRESERVATION LEMMA). *For every abstract graphs \hat{g} and \hat{g}' , abstract store $\hat{\rho}$, concrete graph g , concrete store ρ , set of locations L , property p , and index i , such that $\hat{g}, \hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha} g, \rho$ and $\text{AP}_i(\hat{g}, L, p) = \hat{g}'$, it holds that $\hat{g}', \hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha} g, \rho$.*

PROOF. Assume that $\hat{g}, \hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha} g, \rho$ (**H1**), and $AP_i(\hat{g}, L, p) = \hat{g}'$ (**H2**). From **H1**, it follows that:

- **I1**: $\alpha(g) \subseteq \hat{g}$

Applying the Add Property Monotonicity Lemma (B.10) to **H1** and **H2**, we conclude that:

- **I2**: $\hat{g} \subseteq \hat{g}'$

Combining **I1** with **I2**, it follows that:

- **I3**: $\alpha(g) \subseteq \hat{g}'$

I3 establishes the result. □

LEMMA B.12 (STORE SUBSTITUTION LEMMA). *For every abstract graphs \hat{g} and \hat{g}' , abstract store $\hat{\rho}$ and $\hat{\rho}'$, concrete graph g and g' , concrete store ρ and ρ' , sets of locations L and L' , locations l and l' , property p , and index i , such that:*

- $\hat{g}, \hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha} g, \rho$,
- $\hat{\rho}' = \hat{\rho}[i'/i]$,
- $\rho' = \rho[l'/l]$,
- $\alpha(l) = \hat{l}$, and
- $\alpha(l') = \hat{l}'$

It holds that $\hat{\rho}' \sim_{\alpha} \rho'$.

PROOF. Assume that $\hat{g}, \hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha} g, \rho$ (**H1**), $\hat{\rho}' = \hat{\rho}[i'/i]$ (**H2**), $\rho' = \rho[l'/l]$ (**H3**), $\alpha(l) = \hat{l}$ (**H4**), and $\alpha(l') = \hat{l}'$ (**H5**). We want to prove that $\forall x \in \text{dom}(\rho') . \alpha(\rho'(x)) \in \hat{\rho}'(x)$.

[CASE 1] $\rho(x) = l$ (**H6**).

$$\begin{aligned}
 \alpha(\rho'(x)) &= \alpha(\rho[l'/l](x)) && \text{by H3} \\
 &= \alpha(l') && \text{by H6 and definition} \\
 &= \hat{l}' && \text{by H5} \\
 &\subseteq \{\hat{l}'\} \\
 &= \{\hat{l}'\}[i'/i] \\
 &= \{\alpha(\rho(x))\}[i'/i] && \text{by H4 and H6} \\
 &\subseteq \hat{\rho}(x)[i'/i] && \text{by H1} \\
 &= \hat{\rho}[i'/i](x) && \text{by definition} \\
 &= \hat{\rho}'(x) && \text{by H2}
 \end{aligned}$$

[CASE 1] $\rho(x) \neq l$ (**H6**).

$$\begin{aligned}
 \alpha(\rho'(x)) &= \alpha(\rho(x)) && \text{by H6} \\
 &\in \hat{\rho}(x)
 \end{aligned}$$

□

B.3 Proof of Soundness

THEOREM B.13 (SOUNDNESS). *For all graphs \hat{g}, \hat{g}' , g, g' , abstract stores $\hat{\rho}, \hat{\rho}'$, concrete stores ρ, ρ' , heaps h and h' , statement s , and abstraction function α , it holds that:*

$$\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, s \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \rangle \wedge \hat{g}, \hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha} g, \rho \wedge \langle g, \rho, h, s \rangle \Downarrow_c \langle g', h', \rho' \rangle \implies \exists \alpha'. \alpha' \geq \alpha \wedge \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \sim_{\alpha'} g', \rho'$$

PROOF. Assume that $\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, s \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \rangle$ (**H1**), $\langle g, \rho, h, s \rangle \Downarrow_c \langle g', h', \rho' \rangle$ (**H2**), and $\hat{g}, \hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha} g, \rho$ (**H3**). We proceed by induction on the derivation of $\langle g, \rho, h, s \rangle \Downarrow_c \langle g', h', \rho' \rangle$.

[SEQ] $s = s_1; s_2$. From **H1**, it follows that there exists $\hat{g}_1, \hat{\rho}_1$ such that:

- **I1.1**: $\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, s \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}_1, \hat{\rho}_1 \rangle$
- **I1.2**: $\langle \hat{g}_1, \hat{\rho}_1, s_2 \rangle \Downarrow_c \langle \hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \rangle$

From **H2**, it follows that there exists g_1, h_1, ρ_1 such that:

- **I2.1:** $\langle g, \rho, h, s \rangle \Downarrow_c \langle g_1, h_1, \rho_1 \rangle$
- **I2.2:** $\langle g_1, \rho_1, h_1, s_2 \rangle \Downarrow_c \langle g', h', \rho' \rangle$

Applying the induction hypothesis to **I1.1**, **I2.1**, and **H3**, we conclude that there exists α' such that:

- **I3.1:** $\alpha' \geq \alpha$
- **I3.2:** $\hat{g}_1, \hat{\rho}_1 \sim_{\alpha'} g_1, \rho_1$

Applying the induction hypothesis to **I1.2**, **I2.2**, and **I3.2**, we conclude that there exists α'' such that:

- **I4.1:** $\alpha'' \geq \alpha'$
- **I4.2:** $\hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \sim_{\alpha''} g', \rho'$

Combining **3.1** and **4.1**, we conclude that:

- **I5:** $\alpha'' \geq \alpha$

Equations **I4.2** and **I5** establish the result.

[ASSIGN-EXPR] $s = x := e$. From **H1**, it follows that there exists $L \subseteq \wp(\mathcal{L})$ such that:

- **I1.1:** $\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}} = L$
- **I1.2:** $\hat{\rho}' = \hat{\rho}[x \mapsto L]$
- **I1.3:** $\hat{g}' = \hat{g}$

From **H2**, it follows that there exists $l \in \mathcal{L}$ such that:

- **I2.1:** $\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\rho} = l$
- **I2.2:** $\rho' = \rho[x \mapsto l]$
- **I2.3:** $g' = g$

Combining **H3**, **I1.3**, and **I2.3**, it follows that:

- **I3.1:** $\hat{g}' \sim_{\alpha} g'$

Applying the Expression Evaluation Lemma (Lemma B.4) to **I1.1**, **I2.1**, and **H3**, we conclude that there is α' such that:

- **I4.1:** $\alpha' \geq \alpha$
- **I4.2:** $\alpha'(l) \in L$

Applying the α -Extension Lemma (Lemma B.5) to **I3.1** and **I3.2**, we conclude that:

- **I5.1:** $\hat{g}' \sim_{\alpha'} g'$
- **I5.2:** $\hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha'} \rho$

Applying the Store Update Lemma (Lemma B.6) to **I1.2**, **I2.2**, **I5.2**, and **I4.2**, it follows that:

- **I6.1:** $\hat{\rho}' \sim_{\alpha'} \rho'$

Combining **I5.1** and **I6.1**, we conclude that:

- **I7.1:** $\hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \sim_{\alpha'} g', \rho'$

Equations **I4.1** and **I7.1** establish the result.

[ASSIGN-OP] $s = x :=_i e_1 \oplus e_2$. From **H1**, it follows that there are two sets of locations L_1, L_2 , such that:

- **I1.1:** $\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}} = L_1$
- **I1.2:** $\llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}} = L_2$
- **I1.3:** $\hat{\rho}' = \hat{\rho}[x \mapsto \{\hat{l}_i\}]$
- **I1.4:** $\hat{g}' = \hat{g} \uplus \{l \mapsto_D \hat{l}_i \mid l \in L_1 \cup L_2\}$

From **H2**, it follows that there are three locations l_1, l_2 , and l , such that:

- **I2.1:** $\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\rho} = l_1$

- **I2.2:** $\llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_\rho = l_2$
- **I2.3:** $\rho' = \rho[x \mapsto l]$
- **I2.4:** $g' = g \uplus \{l_i \mapsto_D l \mid_{i=1}^2\}$

Applying the Expression Evaluation Lemma (Lemma B.4) to **I1.1**, **I2.1**, and **H3**, we conclude that there is α' such that:

- **I3.1:** $\alpha' \geq \alpha$
- **I3.2:** $\alpha'(l_1) \in L_1$

Applying the α -Extension Lemma (Lemma B.5) to **I3.1** and **H3**, we conclude that:

- **I4:** $\hat{g}, \hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha'} g, \rho$

Applying the Expression Evaluation Lemma (Lemma B.4) to **I1.2**, **I2.2**, and **I4**, we conclude that there is α'' such that:

- **I5.1:** $\alpha'' \geq \alpha'$
- **I5.2:** $\alpha''(l_2) \in L_2$

Combining **I3.2** and **I5.1**, we conclude that:

- **I6:** $\alpha''(l_1) \in L_1$

Applying the α -Extension Lemma (Lemma B.5) to **I5.1** and **I4**, we conclude that:

- **I7:** $\hat{g}, \hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha''} g, \rho$

Take α''' to be $\alpha''[l \mapsto \hat{l}_i]$, it follows that:

- **I8.1:** $\alpha''' \geq \alpha''$ because l is fresh
- **I8.2:** $\alpha'''(l) \in \{\hat{l}_i\}$

Applying the α -Extension Lemma (Lemma B.5) to **I7** and **I8.1**, we conclude that:

- **I9:** $\hat{g}, \hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha'''} g, \rho$

Applying the Store Update Lemma (Lemma B.6) to **I1.9**, **I1.3**, **I2.3**, and **I8.2**, it follows that:

- **I10:** $\hat{\rho}' \sim_{\alpha'''} \rho'$

From **I8.1**, **I5.2** and **I6**, we conclude that:

- **I11.1** $\alpha'''(l_1) \in L_1$
- **I11.2** $\alpha'''(l_2) \in L_2$

From **I11** and **I8.2**, we conclude that:

- **I12.1** $\alpha'''(l_1 \mapsto_D l) \in \{l \mapsto_D \hat{l}_i \mid l \in L_1\}$
- **I12.2** $\alpha'''(l_2 \mapsto_D l) \in \{l \mapsto_D \hat{l}_i \mid l \in L_2\}$

From **I12**, it follows that:

- **I13:** $\alpha'''(\{l_1 \mapsto_D l, l_2 \mapsto_D l\}) \subseteq \{l \mapsto_D \hat{l}_i \mid l \in L_1 \cup L_2\}$
 $\Leftrightarrow \{l \mapsto_D \hat{l}_i \mid l \in L_1 \cup L_2\} \sim_{\alpha'''} \{l_1 \mapsto_D l, l_2 \mapsto_D l\}$

Equations **I4.1** and **I7.1** establish the result. Applying Correctness Preservation for Graph Union to **I1.4**, **I2.4**, **I9** and **I13**, we conclude that:

- **I14:** $\hat{g}' \sim_{\alpha'''} g'$

Combining **I10** and **I4**, it follows that:

- **I15:** $\hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \sim_{\alpha'''} g', \rho'$

Combining **3.1**, **5.1** and **8.1**, we conclude that:

- **I16:** $\alpha''' \geq \alpha$

Equations **I15** and **I16** establish the result.

[NEW OBJECT] $s = x := \{ \}^i$. From **H1**, it follows that:

- **I1.1:** $\hat{g}' = \hat{g} \uplus \{\hat{l}_i \mapsto_F l_f\}$
- **I1.2:** $\hat{\rho}' = \hat{\rho}[x \mapsto \{\hat{l}_i\}]$

From **H2**, it follows that there is a fresh location l such that:

- **I2.1:** $g' = g \uplus \{l \mapsto_F l_f\}$
- **I2.2:** $\rho = \rho[x \mapsto l]$

Take α' to be $\alpha[l \mapsto \hat{l}_i]$, it follows that:

- **I3:** $\alpha' \geq \alpha$ because l is fresh

Applying the α -Extension Lemma (Lemma B.5) to **H3** and **I3**, we conclude that:

- **I4:** $\hat{g}, \hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha'} g, \rho$

Noting that $\alpha(l \mapsto_F l_f) = \hat{l}_i \mapsto_F l_f$, we conclude, using the Correctness Preservation (Graph Inclusion) Lemma on **H3**, **I1.1**, **I1.2**, that:

- **I5:** $\hat{g}' \sim_{\alpha} g'$

Applying the Store Update Lemma (Lemma B.6) to **I1.2**, **I2.2**, and **I4**, noting that $\alpha'(l) \in \{\hat{l}_i\}$, we conclude that:

- **I6:** $\hat{\rho}' \sim_{\alpha'} \rho'$

Combining **I5** and **I6**, it follows that:

- **I7:** $\hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \sim_{\alpha'} g', \rho'$

Equations **I3** and **I7** establish the result.

[PROPERTY LOOKUP] $s = x :=_i e.p$. From **H1**, it follows that there is an abstract graph \hat{g}' and two sets of locations L, L' , such that:

- **I1.1:** $\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}} = L$
- **I1.2:** $\hat{g}' = \text{AP}_i(\hat{g}, L, p)$
- **I1.3:** $L' = \{l' \mid l \in L \wedge \hat{g}[l, p] = l'\}$
- **I1.4:** $\hat{\rho}' = \hat{\rho}[x \mapsto L']$

From **H2**, it follows that there is a location l' , such that:

- **I2.1:** $\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\rho} = l'$
- **I2.2:** $g[l, p] = l'$
- **I2.3:** $\rho' = \rho[x \mapsto l']$

Applying the Expression Evaluation Lemma (Lemma B.4) to **I1.1**, **I2.1**, and **H3**, we conclude that there is α' such that:

- **I3.1:** $\alpha' \geq \alpha$
- **I3.2:** $\alpha'(l) \in L$

Applying the α -Extension Lemma (Lemma B.5) to **H3** and **I3.1**, we conclude that:

- **I4:** $\hat{g}, \hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha'} g, \rho$

Applying the Add Property Preservation Lemma (Lemma B.11) to **I1.2** and **I4**, it follows that:

- **I5:** $\hat{g}', \hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha'} g, \rho$

Applying the Property Lookup Lemma (Lemma B.9) to **I2.2** and **I5**, it follows that:

- **I6:** $\alpha'(l') \in \hat{g}'[\alpha'(l), p]$

Combining **I6** and **I5**, it follows that:

- **I7:** $\alpha'(l) \in L'$

Applying the Store Update Lemma (Lemma B.6) to **I1.4**, **I2.3**, **I5**, and **I7**, it follows that:

- **I8:** $\hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \sim_{\alpha'} g, \rho'$

Equations **I3.1** and **I8** establish the result.

[PROPERTY UPDATE] $s = e_1.p :=_i e_2$. From **H1**, it follows that there is an abstract graph \hat{g}'' and three sets of locations L_1, L_2, L'_1 , such that:

- **I1.1:** $\llbracket e_i \rrbracket_{\hat{\rho}} = L_i \mid_{i=1,2}$
- **I1.2:** $(\hat{g}'', \hat{\rho}', L'_1) = \text{NV}_i(\hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, L_1, p)$
- **I1.3:** $\hat{g}' = \hat{g}'' \uplus \{l_1 \mapsto_{\text{P}(p)} l_2 \mid l_1 \in L'_1 \wedge l_2 \in L_2\}$

From **H2**, we conclude that there is a concrete graph g'' , and three locations l', l_1 , and l_2 , such that:

- **I2.1:** $\llbracket e_i \rrbracket_{\rho} = l_i \mid_{i=1,2}$
- **I2.2:** $(g'', \rho', l') = \text{NV}_c(g)\rho l_1 p$
- **I2.3:** $g' = g'' \uplus \{l' \mapsto_{\text{P}(p)} l_2\}$

Applying the Expression Evaluation Lemma (Lemma B.4) to **I1.1**, **I2.1**, and **H3**, we conclude that there is α' such that:

- **I3.1:** $\alpha' \geq \alpha$
- **I3.2:** $\alpha'(l_1) \in L_1$
- **I3.3:** $\alpha'(l_2) \in L_2$

Applying the α -Extension Lemma (Lemma B.5) to **H3** and **I3.1**, we conclude that:

- **I4:** $\hat{g}, \hat{\rho} \sim_{\alpha'} g, \rho$

Applying the New Version Lemma (Lemma B.8) to **I1.2**, **2.2**, **I3.2**, and **I4**, we conclude that there is α'' such that:

- **I5.1:** $\alpha'' \geq \alpha$
- **I5.2:** $\hat{g}'', \hat{\rho}' \sim_{\alpha''} g'', \rho'$
- **I5.3:** $\alpha''(l') \in L'_1$

From **I3.3** and **I5.1**, it follows that:

- **I6:** $\alpha''(l_2) \in L_2$

We now want to establish that:

$$\alpha''(l' \mapsto_{\text{P}(p)} l_2) \in \{l_1 \mapsto_{\text{P}(p)} l_2 \mid l_1 \in L'_1 \wedge l_2 \in L_2\} \quad (\text{I7})$$

The proof of **I7** goes as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \alpha''(l' \mapsto_{\text{P}(p)} l_2) \\ &= \alpha''(l') \mapsto_{\text{P}(p)} \alpha''(l_2) && \text{by definition} \\ &\in \{l_1 \mapsto_{\text{P}(p)} \alpha''(l_2) \mid l_1 \in L'_1\} && \text{by I5.3} \\ &\subseteq \{l_1 \mapsto_{\text{P}(p)} l_2 \mid l_1 \in L'_1 \wedge l_2 \in L_2\} && \text{by I6} \end{aligned}$$

Applying Correctness Preservation for Graph Union to **I1.3**, **2.3**, **I5.2**, **I7**, we conclude that:

- **I8:** $\hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \sim_{\alpha''} g', \rho'$

Equations **I5.1** and **I8** establish the result.

[IF - TRUE] $s = \text{if}(e_1)\{s_1\} \text{ else } \{s_2\}$. From **H1**, it follows that there is an abstract graph \hat{g}'_1 and an abstract store $\hat{\rho}'_1$, such that:

- **I1.1:** $\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, s_1 \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}_1, \hat{\rho}_1 \rangle$
- **I1.2:** $\langle \hat{g}, \hat{\rho}, s_2 \rangle \Downarrow_s \langle \hat{g}_2, \hat{\rho}_2 \rangle$
- **I1.3:** $\hat{g}' = \hat{g}_1 \sqcup \hat{g}_2$
- **I1.4:** $\hat{\rho}' = \hat{\rho}_1 \sqcup \hat{\rho}_2$

From **H2**, it follows that there is a location l , such that:

- **I2.1:** $\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\rho} = l$

- **I2.2:** $h(l) = true$
- **I2.3:** $\langle g, h, \rho, s_1 \rangle \Downarrow_c \langle g', h', \rho' \rangle$

Applying the induction hypothesis to **I1.1**, **I2.3**, and **H3**, we conclude that there exists α' such that:

- **I3.1** $\alpha' \geq \alpha$
- **I3.2** $\hat{g}_1, \hat{\rho}_1 \sim_{\alpha'} g', \rho'$

From **I1.3** and **I1.4**, it follows that:

- **I4** $\hat{g}_1, \hat{\rho}_1 \sqsubseteq g', \rho'$

Applying Correctness Preservation for Storage Union to **I3.1** and **I4**, it follows that:

- **I5:** $\hat{g}', \hat{\rho}' \sim_{\alpha'} g', \rho'$

Equations **I3.1** and **I5** establish the result.

□